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The formation of autocephaly of the Church of Poland in the 20th century

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Abstract

Following the end of World War I and the establishment of the independent Polish state, the Church of Poland appealed to the Ecumenical Patriarchate, requesting the bestowal of the ecclesiastical status of autocephaly. The mother Church of Constantinople, for both canonical and historical reasons, issued a Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos on November 13, 1924, granting full ecclesiastical independence to the Church of Poland. However, in 1939, with the Nazi invasion of Poland and the occupation of its eastern part by Soviet troops, the Orthodox Church found itself in an extremely difficult position, resulting in attempts by the Church of Russia to subjugate it. This led to the so-called «Polish issue» in 1948, which was resolved by Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras I in 1961. Given this year marks the centenary (1924-2024) of the granting of autocephaly to the Church of Poland, this article offers the opportunity to honor this significant event by highlighting its historical importance and to study the conditions that led to the inclusion of the Church of Poland in the family of Orthodox Autocephalous Churches.

Introduction

Christianity spread to the territories of modern Poland in the late 9th to early 10th century, and its dissemination was associated with the missionary work of the Thessalonian brothers, Cyril and Methodius.³ After the death

³ The Christianization achieved through the missionary work led by saints Cyril and Methodius assisted the Slavic nations in strengthening their state authority, social organization, educational development, and, most importantly, their entry into the community of civilized peoples. Ultimately, it determined their entrance into history. For all these reasons, the saints are not only accorded religious honors but also receive broader recognition and prominence. In this

of Saint Methodius in 885, and especially following the persecutions against his disciples, the significant efforts by the Byzantine missionaries were disrupted, while the field was left open to the Frankish missionaries.⁴ This situation contributed both to the official conversion of the Poles to Christianity by the Frankish missionaries and to their submission to the jurisdiction of the papal throne in 966.⁵ Notably, one of the students and successors of the Thessalonian brothers was Gorazd, who is considered the founder of Orthodoxy in Poland.⁶

The consolidation of Christianity in Poland occurred gradually and was influenced both by the expansion of the Polish state and by the guardianship of the German kings. The simultaneous consolidation of Christianity among neighboring Slavic peoples, particularly the Russians and Lithuanians, was significantly affected by the activities of the Byzantine missionary efforts.⁷

The official conversion of the Grand Prince of Kiev, Vladimir (960-1015), leader of the Rus' state, and his people in 988 was linked to the work of the Byzantine missionary effort in the autonomous principalities of Russia and Lithuania, centered around the Metropolitan See of Kiev and All Rus', which was under the jurisdiction of the Ecumenical Patriarchate. This jurisdiction also included the local Churches of Lithuania and the eastern regions of Poland.⁸ The division of the Metropolitan See of Kiev and All

way, the respect of the Slavs towards Byzantium and the Ecumenical Throne, from which this mission was organized, is manifested. This mission continues to bear fruit, as the language created by the saints has come to serve as a unifying medium for all Slavs to this day. P. Christou, *Κύριλλος και Μεθόδιος, οί Θεσσαλονικεῖς Φωτισταί τῶν Σλάβων (Cyril and Methodius, the Thessalonian Enlighteners of the Slavs)*, Kyromanos: Thessaloniki 1988, pp. 53, 64.

⁴ See in detail for the Church of Poland: P. Tzoumerkas, « Η αυτοκέφαλη ορθόδοξη Εκκλησία της Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland)», in *National and Religious Contemporary Issues* vol. II, Pournaras publications: Thessaloniki 2005, pp. 281–344.

⁵ V. Feidas, *Εκκλησιαστική Ιστορία Γ' – Από την Άλωση μέχρι σήμερα – 1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III – From the Fall to Today – 1453–2014)*, Athens 2014, p. 604.

⁶ P. Tzoumerkas, « Η αυτοκέφαλη ορθόδοξη Εκκλησία της Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland)», op. cit., p. 283.

⁷ V. Feidas, *Εκκλησιαστική Ιστορία Γ' – Από την Άλωση μέχρι σήμερα – 1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III – From the Fall to Today – 1453–2014)*, op. cit., p. 604.

⁸ The existence of the metropolis of Krakow is attested well before the emergence

Rus' was crucial for the future of the Orthodox bishops⁹ who had been annexed under the dominion of the rulers of Poland and Lithuania, as it hastened the union of Orthodox Lithuania with Roman Catholic Poland in 1569 to jointly face the threat of Greater Russia. This union favored the unfair practices of the papal Uniate movement in the Orthodox territories of «Lesser» and «White» Russia under Polish or Lithuanian dominion.¹⁰

The annexation of «Lesser» Russia, including Kiev, to Greater Russia following the Russo-Polish Peace Treaty of 1686, was accompanied by the conditional consent of Dionysius III (1615-1696), Patriarch of Constantinople, for the subjugation of the Metropolitan See of Kiev to the Patriarchate of Moscow, designated as a «patriarchal exarchate» of the throne of Constantinople in 1687.¹¹ However, this act by Patriarch Dionysius III was canonically invalid, as it contravened the 34th Apostolic Canon and the 9th Canon of Antioch, which prohibit the primate from acting without the opinion of other Hierarchs. Furthermore, the act was invalid as a deed of tyrannical force, according to the general principle of law. Moreover, even the conditions set by Patriarch Dionysius III for the commemoration of his name before all others in every ceremony were violated by the Russian Church.¹²

The organized opposition to Russian policies led to three consecutive

of the metropolis of Kiev and the advent of the Latin ecclesiastical rhythm. P. Tzoumerkas, «Η αυτοκέφαλη ορθόδοξη Εκκλησία της Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland),» *op. cit.*, p. 283.

⁹ The metropolis of Kiev was under the canonical jurisdiction of the Ecumenical Patriarchate, while metropolitans of Kiev such as Petro Mohyla (1596–1647), Sylvester Kossov, and Dionysius Balaban categorically rejected any administrative dependency on the Patriarchate of Moscow. V. Feidas, *Εκκλησιαστική Ιστορία Γ'—Από την άλωση μέχρι σήμερα—1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III—From the Fall to Today—1453–2014)*, *op. cit.*, p. 613.

¹⁰ See related: A. Borkowski, *Αγώνας τῶν Ὀρθοδόξων Πατριαρχείων κατὰ τῆς Οὐνίας στὴν Πολωνία κατὰ τὴν τελευταία εἰκοσαετία τοῦ ΙΣΤ' αἰῶνα—1583–1601 (The Struggle of the Orthodox Patriarchates against the Union in Poland during the Last Two Decades of the 16th Century—1583–1601)*, PhD Thesis, University of Athens, Athens 2008.

¹¹ V. Feidas, *Εκκλησιαστική Ιστορία Γ'—Από την άλωση μέχρι σήμερα—1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III—From the Fall to Today—1453–2014)*, *op. cit.*, p. 614.

¹² Special Commission Report dated November 6, 1924: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod.

partitions of Poland in 1772, 1793, and 1795, with Russia, Austria, and Prussia competing for the distribution of its territories until the final dissolution of the Polish state in 1795. Most of the territories were acquired by Russia, and many Orthodox Christians came under the jurisdiction of the Russian Church, influenced by overt tsarist political pressure. However, the Orthodox populations in the regions annexed by Austria and Prussia remained under the influence of the Roman Catholic Church. The Grand Duchy of Warsaw, established by Napoleon after his victory against Prussia in 1807, eventually fell under Russian control after Napoleon's defeat in Russia in 1812.¹³ At the Congress of Vienna in 1815, the territory was redistributed: the Duchy of Poznań was assigned to Prussia, Galicia to Austria, and the majority of the Warsaw Duchy's lands were designated as the «Kingdom of Poland» under Russian control, after Emperor of Russia Alexander I (1777–1825) guaranteed administrative autonomy and the granting of a constitution. However, following the failure of the Polish uprising in 1830–1831, Russian forces captured Warsaw on September 8, 1831, and committed unspeakable atrocities in all the revolted areas, while the leaders of the revolution were imprisoned or exiled to Siberia.¹⁴ The 1815 constitution was abolished, and the Kingdom of Poland was subjected to the Tsarist Senate. Concurrently, the universities of Warsaw and Vilnius were shut down. Additionally, a systematic Russification of the Poles was carried out through administrative and educational programs.¹⁵

Despite these challenges, resistance continued and Poland fought against Russian occupation. The prudent choice by the socialist leader of the «patriotic wing,» Józef Klemens Piłsudski (1867–1935),¹⁶ during the early years of World War I to reject both Russia's proposals for autonomy and the German and Austrian proposal to establish a «Kingdom of Poland»

¹³ J. Stanley, «The French Residents in the Duchy of Warsaw,» *Canadian Slavonic Papers* 27 (1985), pp. 49–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00085006.1985.11091793>

¹⁴ R. F. Leslie, «Polish Political Divisions and the Struggle for Power at the Beginning of the Insurrection of November 1830,» *The Slavonic and East European Review* 76 (1952), pp. 113–32. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4204407>

¹⁵ V. Feidas, *Εκκλησιαστική Ιστορία Γ'—Από την Άλωση μέχρι σήμερα—1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III—From the Fall to Today—1453–2014)*, op. cit., p. 615.

¹⁶ M. Klimecki, «Józef Piłsudski in the history of Poland and Europe. Introduction to the biography,» *Analele Științifice ale Universității Alexandru Ioan Cuz din Iași. Istorie* 63 (2017), pp. 11–21.

in 1916, facilitated the internationalization of the Polish issue and led to the proclamation of the independent Republic of Poland on November 11, 1918. Within the borders of the new state, which ecclesiastically remained under the jurisdiction of the Ecumenical Patriarchate as part of the old Metropolitan See of Kiev, there were about four million Orthodox Christians of Russian, Ukrainian, and Polish descent. These communities were well-organized and made significant spiritual and social contributions, and, along with the Polish government, sought the emancipation of their ecclesiastical life.¹⁷

The granting of autocephaly to the Church of Poland

The Orthodox Church of Poland,¹⁸ with the consent of the Polish government, approached the Ecumenical Patriarchate and requested that the mother Church of Constantinople grant it autocephalous status.¹⁹ For this purpose, on June 14, 1924, hierarchs from the Church of Poland visited the Ecumenical Patriarchate to officially request the granting of full ecclesiastical independence to the Church of Poland.²⁰ The Holy and Sacred

¹⁷ V. Feidas, *Ἐκκλησιαστικὴ Ἱστορία Γ'—Ἀπὸ τὴν ἄλωση μέχρι σήμερον—1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III—From the Fall to Today—1453–2014)*, op. cit., p. 616–17.

¹⁸ The first metropolitan of Warsaw, Georgios (1872–1923), convened a synod on June 14, 1922, with the four Orthodox bishops within the borders of the Polish state. With a vote of 3-2, they decided in favor of declaring autocephaly. Following the assassination of metropolitan Georgios and severe attacks from Roman Catholics, the issue became urgent. P. Tzoumerkas, «Ἡ αυτοκέφαλη ὀρθόδοξη Ἐκκλησία τῆς Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland)», op. cit., p. 314–115.

¹⁹ It is a fact that Metropolitan Dionysios of Warsaw attempted to communicate with the venerable Patriarch Tikhon of Moscow, but all his efforts were fruitless. Moreover, if the Ecumenical Patriarchate had not intervened to organize the Church of Poland and subsequently contributed to the endorsement of its Constitution by the Polish State, thus ensuring its protection under the laws, it is not unlikely that the Church of Poland would have become a prey to Catholicism. At that time, Catholicism represented the official Church of the State and had perfect organization and strength, as well as ample means to conduct proselytism on a wide scale, especially since it exerted tremendous pressure to prevent the ratification of the Constitutional Charter.

²⁰ P. Tzoumerkas, «Ἡ αυτοκέφαλη ὀρθόδοξη Ἐκκλησία τῆς Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland)», op. cit., p. 303. M. Fouyias, Archbishop of Thyateira and Great Britain, «Σύστασις τῆς Ὀρθοδόξου Ἐκ-

Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate referred the matter to a special committee chaired by Metropolitan Kallinikos of Cyzicus (1855–1934), later Metropolitan of Caesarea (Kaisareia), and including Metropolitan Joachim of Chalcedon (1876–1927), Metropolitan Agathangelos of Prince’s Islands (1864–1935), later Metropolitan of Ephesus, and Metropolitan Germanos of Sardis (1885–1945). The committee thoroughly examined the issue from historical and canonical perspectives, alongside letters from metropolitan Dionysius of Warsaw (1876–1960) regarding the ecclesiastical situation in Poland²¹ and other relevant documents from the Polish Embassy in Constantinople. Additionally, the committee held a special meeting with the Polish Ambassador in Constantinople, Mr. Kół, who presented the views of the Polish Government.²²

The committee submitted its findings on November 6, 1924, concluding that the Orthodox Christians of Poland were not canonically subordinated to the Church of Russia. Therefore, the Church of Constantinople was entitled to grant them full ecclesiastical independence. The report specifically stated: «Consequently, the Orthodox of the Kingdom of Poland, not having been subjected to the Church of Russia according to the established canonical formalities, the Church of Constantinople is entitled to take the appropriate maternal care of them. This is all the more true as these Orthodox now find themselves in a state independent from Russia, which automatically triggers the application of the rules of the 17th Canon of the Fourth Ecumenical Council and the 38th Canon of the Quinisext Council. According to these canons, ‘the ecclesiastical order of public and political places shall follow,’ which Saint Photios interprets as ‘the ecclesiastical affairs, especially those concerning parishes, ought to adapt to the political

κλησίας Πολωνίας και τὸ αὐτοκέφαλον αὐτῆς (Constitution of the Orthodox Church of Poland and its Autocephaly),» *Archive of Ecclesiastical and Canonical Law* 12 (1957), p. 42.

²¹ The Church of Poland maintained canonical communication with the Ecumenical Patriarchate even before the application for autocephaly. For instance, the Archbishop of Warsaw, Dionysius, informed the Ecumenical Patriarchate that the New Calendar had been implemented in the Church of Poland, which came into effect across Poland from the Sunday of All Saints. «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΚΩΝ)ΠΟΛΕΩΣ,» *Πάνταινος* 27 (July 5, 1924), p. 456. «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ,» *Πάνταινος* 42 (October 18, 1924), p. 706.

²² «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΚΩΝΣΤΑΝΤΙΝΟΥΠΟΛΕΩΝ,» *Ἐκκλησία* 25 (November 15, 1924), p. 189. «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ,» *Πάνταινος* 44 (November 1, 1924), p. 733.

sovereignties and administrations’ .»²³

The Holy and Sacred Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate convened immediately after the submission of the aforementioned report on November 6, and revisited the issue during its session on November 11.²⁴ During these sessions, the Synod duly evaluated the committee’s report along with the various political, ecclesiastical, and pastoral aspects of the issue and decided to grant full ecclesiastical independence to the Church of Poland. Consequently, on November 13, 1924, the Ecumenical Patriarch Gregory VII (1850–1924) issued a Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos,²⁵ which defined the canonical criteria for both the internal administrative organization of the newly established Church and its relations with the Ecumenical Patriarchate and the other autocephalous Orthodox Churches.²⁶

According to the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos, the autocephaly of the Church of Poland was founded on the independent Polish state and on the jurisdiction of the Ecumenical Patriarchate over the old Metropolitan See of Kiev, from which the Orthodox Churches of Lithuania and Poland were dependent. The highest ecclesiastical authority of the Church of Poland was established as the Holy Synod of Bishops, presided over by the respective «Most Reverend»²⁷ metropolitan of Warsaw and all Poland.²⁸ To maintain

²³ Special Commission Report dated November 6, 1924: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod.

²⁴ Session of the Holy and Sacred Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate dated November 6, 1924: Archive B’ 71. Session of the Holy and Sacred Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate dated November 11, 1924: Archive B’ 71.

²⁵ The Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos was signed not only by the Ecumenical Patriarch but also by the Metropolitans of Cyzicus Callinicos, Nicaea Vasilios, Chalcedon Ioakeim, Derkon Constantine, Bursa Nikodemos, Prince’s Islands Agathangelos, Neocaesarea Ambrosios, Sardes and Pisidia Germanos, Philadelphia Fotios, Selymbria Eugenios, Rodopolis Cyril, and Aneon Thomas.

²⁶ Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos regarding the Recognition of the Autocephaly of the Holy Orthodox Church in Poland, in *Ὁρθοδοξία* I (1926–1927), pp. 36–38.

²⁷ The title of «His Beatitude» was later granted to the Primate of the Church of Poland by a special Patriarchal and Synodal Act.

²⁸ During that period, the Church of Poland had the following hierarchical structure: A. Five dioceses: 1. Warsaw—Cholm, 2. Volhynia—Kremenets, 3. Vilnius—Lida, 4. Grodno—Novogrudok, 5. Pinsk—Polesia B. Four ruling bishops: 1. Metropolitan of Warsaw, Dionysius, 2. Archbishop of Vilnius and Lida, Theodosius (1864–1943), 3. Bishop of Pinsk and Polesia, Alexander (1887–1948), 4. Bishop of Grodno and Novogrudok, Alexis (1882–1943) C.

and demonstrate canonical unity with the Ecumenical Patriarchate and the other Autocephalous Orthodox Churches, the Metropolitan of Warsaw is obligated to: 1) officially announce his election through enthronement letters to the Ecumenical Patriarchate and other Autocephalous Churches, 2) commemorate the name of the Ecumenical Patriarch and other Patriarchs and Heads of Autocephalous Churches in the Diptychs, 3) receive the Holy Myrrh from the Ecumenical Patriarchate,²⁹ and 4) address the Ecumenical Patriarchate concerning broader ecclesiastical matters or questions that exceed the jurisdiction of the individual Autocephalous Churches and through this to seek the valid opinion and understanding of the other Churches.³⁰

The Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople, immediately after elevating a Church to autocephaly, announced the event through a letter to the ancient Patriarchates and the other autocephalous Churches. However, Ecumenical Patriarch Gregory VII passed away four days after signing the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos,³¹ and the elevation of the Church of Poland to autocephaly was announced to the other Churches on January 13, 1925, by his successor, Ecumenical Patriarch Constantine VI (1859–1930), almost two months after granting full ecclesiastical independence to the said Church.³²

After the signing of the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos, the head of the newly established autocephalous Church of Poland expressed his

Two auxiliary bishops of the Holy Metropolis of Warsaw: 1. Bishop of Lublin, Anthony (1887–1954), 2. Bishop of Kremenets, Simon (1888–1966).

²⁹ Because Metropolitan Dionysius's visit was delayed due to circumstances, the Holy Myrrh was sent to the newly established Church from the Ecumenical Patriarchate in early April 1926. «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ», in *Ἐκκλησία* 22 (May 28, 1926), p. 174.

³⁰ Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos on the Recognition of the Autocephaly of the Holy Orthodox Church in Poland, *Ὁρθοδοξία* I (1926–1927), pp. 36–38.

³¹ In the speech delivered by the Secretary of the Holy and Sacred Synod, Dorotheios, during the funeral of Patriarch Gregory VII, he referred to «his praiseworthy action» as «the emancipation from his bed of illness by the illustrious Patriarch of an old daughter of the Patriarchate (the Church of Poland). «Ἡ δράσις του Γρηγορίου Ζ' (The Actions of Gregory VII),» in *Πάπταινος* 47 (November 22, 1924), p. 781.

³² Letter from Ecumenical Patriarch Constantine VI to the Primates of the Orthodox Churches, Prot. No. 192 dated January 13, 1925: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod.

intention to visit the Ecumenical Patriarchate and the other autocephalous Churches.³³ However, due to circumstances, metropolitan Dionysius officially visited the Ecumenical Patriarchate almost three years later, from April 6 to 10, 1927. On April 7, he was awarded the title of «His Beatitude» by Ecumenical Patriarch Basil III (1840–1929) through a special Patriarchal and Synodal Act, «so that the numerous and thus proven worthy beloved sister Orthodox Church of Poland would not be inferior in title to the presiding, achieving equality with the other Holy Sister Orthodox Autocephalous Churches.»³⁴

Prior to this, the official delivery of the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos took place on November 17, 1925, by a special patriarchal delegation that traveled to Poland for this purpose. The delegation consisted of metropolitan Joachim of Chalcedon, Metropolitan Germanos of Sardis, and the interpreter of the Patriarchates, Spiros Konstantinidis. The ceremony was given exceptional splendor by the Polish government, with the participation of a representative of the political leadership. During the ceremony, while the national anthem of Poland was played, the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos was read in Greek, Russian, and Ukrainian.³⁵

The organization of the autocephalous Church of Poland

Following the signing of the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos, the Holy Synod of the newly established Church of Poland convened under the chairmanship of metropolitan Dionysius of Warsaw, aiming to draft the Constitutional Charter of the now autocephalous Church.³⁶ The pressing issue at that time was the legal status of the Church of Poland within the Polish State. For this reason, the Church of Poland focused on arranging its internal position by drafting legislation that would secure «the privileges belonging to it and the position corresponding to its mission.»³⁷ Two main points were predominant between the Church and the State in Poland: 1. the issue of the property of the Orthodox Church, and 2. the issue of the personal rights of its clergy.³⁸

³³ «ΟΡΘΟΔΟΞΟΣ ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ», in *Ἐκκλησία* 44-45 (November 6, 1925), p. 367.

³⁴ *Ὁρθοδοξία* II (1927–28), pp. 87–88.

³⁵ P. Tzoumerkias, «Ἡ αὐτοκέφαλη ὀρθόδοξη Ἐκκλησία τῆς Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland)», op. cit., p. 305.

³⁶ «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ», *Ἐκκλησία* 49 (December 4, 1925), p. 400.

³⁷ «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ», *Ἐκκλησία* 14 (April 2, 1926), p. 110.

³⁸ «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ», *Ἐκκλησία* 16 (April 16, 1926), pp. 126–127

Despite the obstacles and problems posed by both the Roman Catholic Church and the government, metropolitan Dionysius remained undeterred.³⁹ The struggle of the Church of Poland to secure an institutional framework for its legal status and its relations with the Polish state was successfully crowned nearly 14 years later.⁴⁰ On November 18, 1938, the Polish government ratified the «Internal Statute» (Statut Wewnetrzny) of the Church of Poland by presidential decree. This Statute recognized the «Most Blessed Orthodox Archbishop of Warsaw and Metropolitan of Poland» as the head of the autocephalous Orthodox Church, who was also the supreme representative of the Church in its relations with the Polish government. The central administrative bodies were designated as the Holy Synod under the presidency of the Metropolitan and the general clerical-laity assembly (Sobor Generalny) of the Church of Poland. Additionally, as provincial administrative bodies, the local bishop and the clerical-laity council of each province were established.⁴¹

Another significant internal issue that the Church of Poland had to face was the diverse national origins of the Orthodox faithful. This problem manifested primarily as a language issue, given that Old Church Slavonic was the official language for all liturgical ceremonies. Ukrainian-origin faithful convened a lay conference in Potsk and attempted to impose the translation of liturgical texts into Ukrainian. However, the Church of Poland reacted promptly and organized a conference at the Pochaev Monastery, presided over by metropolitan Dionysius, where the inadequacy of Ukrainian as a liturgical language was demonstrated. It was also shown that Old Church Slavonic was the best choice. Nonetheless, it was agreed that sermons could be delivered in the vernacular languages of the people, including Polish, Russian, and Ukrainian.⁴²

³⁹ P. Tzoumerkas, «Η αυτοκέφαλη ὀρθόδοξη Ἐκκλησία τῆς Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland)», *op. cit.*, p. 306.

⁴⁰ See related: P. Tzoumerkas, Ἀνέκδοτο σημεῖωμα τοῦ Μητροπολίτη Σάρδεων Γερμανοῦ γιὰ τὴν κατάσταση τῆς Ὁρθόδοξης Ἐκκλησίας τῆς Πολωνίας τὸ 1930 (Unpublished note by Metropolitan Germanos of Sardes on the status of the Orthodox Church of Poland in 1930), in *ΚΟΣΜΟΣ/COSMOS* 7 (2020), pp. 75–128.

⁴¹ V. Feidas, *Ἐκκλησιαστικὴ Ἱστορία Γ'—Ἀπὸ τὴν ἄλωση μέχρι σήμερον—1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III—From the Fall to Today—1453–2014)*, *op. cit.*, p. 620.

⁴² P. Tzoumerkas, «Η αυτοκέφαλη ὀρθόδοξη Ἐκκλησία τῆς Πολωνίας (The

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Following its autocephalous organization and subsequent actions, the Church of Poland was fully integrated into the family of the Autocephalous Orthodox Churches. It participated in the works of the Inter-Orthodox Committee convened at Mount Athos in 1930. The Church was personally represented by its primate, Metropolitan Dionysius. At the start of the committee's work, which was chaired by metropolitan Philaretos of Heraclea (1850-1933), representative of the Ecumenical Patriarch, metropolitan Dionysius declared: «On behalf of the Polish Church, I address this Assembly as a visible expression of the internal unity of the individual Orthodox Churches, orchestrated under the guidance of the Church of Constantinople, which by virtue of its antiquity, holds its unique spirit. The Polish Church, being young, feels particularly the need for communication with the other Churches, to receive spiritual aid and counsel. Therefore, I considered it a sacred duty to appear personally at this Assembly, to draw from it the spirit of Universal Orthodoxy.»⁴³

Additionally, the Church of Poland participated in the conferences of the Ecumenical Movement, Faith and Order (Lausanne 1927 and Edinburgh 1937) and Life and Work (Oxford 1937).⁴⁴ Furthermore, the newly established Theological School of the University of Warsaw commenced operations, appointing new professors including Ogienko for the teaching of Church Slavonic language and paleography, and Archpriest Davidovits for the teaching of Church History and Patrology.⁴⁵ In its first three years, the school acquired 6 professors and 150 students.⁴⁶ Notably, the Orthodox Theological School of the University of Warsaw was represented at the first Pan-Orthodox Theological Conference in Athens in 1936.⁴⁷

Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland),» *op. cit.*, p. 318.

⁴³ Πρακτικά τῆς Προκαταρκτικῆς Επιτροπῆς τῶν Ἁγίων Ὁρθοδόξων Ἐκκλησιῶν τῆς συνελθούσης ἐν τῇ ἐν Ἁγίῳ Ὄρει Ἱερᾷ Μεγίστῃ Μονῇ τοῦ Βατοπεδίου—8–23 Ἰουνίου 1930 (Minutes of the Preliminary Committee of the Holy Orthodox Churches convened at the Holy Mountain in the Vatopedi Monastery—June 8–23, 1930): Constantinople 1930, p. 47.

⁴⁴ «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ,» *Ἐκκλησία* 29–30 (July 22, 1926), p. 238.

⁴⁵ In addition to the Theological School, three ecclesiastical seminaries were also in operation. «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ,» *Ἐκκλησία* 29–30 (July 22, 1926), p. 238.

⁴⁶ «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ,» in *Ἐκκλησία* 6 (February 4, 1927), pp. 47–48.

⁴⁷ V. Stavridis, «Πολωνίας, Ορθόδοξος Ἐκκλησία (Orthodox Church of

By 1939, the Church of Poland had 1,624 parishes, 2,076 churches, and 2,968 clergy members. There were also 16 holy monasteries, of which ten were male and six were female, housing approximately 600 monks and nuns. Additionally, there was an ecclesiastical printing press where the official journal of the Orthodox Church was printed, along with two weekly papers, one in Russian and the other in Ukrainian, as well as various other ecclesiastical publications and theological studies.⁴⁸

The creation of the Polish issue

The Nazi invasion of Poland on September 1, 1939, and the subsequent occupation of the eastern part of the country by Soviet troops placed the Orthodox Church of Poland in an extremely difficult position, facing indescribable violence. The annexation of the eastern part of the country to the Soviet Republic of Belarus brought the majority of the Orthodox under the ecclesiastical jurisdiction of the Church of Russia.⁴⁹ The implementation of the Statute, which had been established with great effort, was no longer possible, and the administration of the metropolis of Warsaw was assigned by the German military leadership to metropolitan Seraphim (1883–1950) in Berlin and Germany, and by the Soviet military leadership to bishop Timothy Szretter (1901–1962), who had already begun negotiations with the Patriarchate of Moscow to abolish the canonical autocephaly of the Church of Poland and subjugate the Polish Church to the Church of Russia. Initially, the primate of the Church of Poland, metropolitan Dionysius, was imprisoned and remained in jail in Kraków for about 18 months, and subsequently was placed under house arrest and forced to recognize in writing the temporary and uncanonical nature of the autocephaly granted in 1924.⁵⁰

Poland),» in *Religious and Ethical Encyclopedia* 10, Athens 1966, p. 544.

⁴⁸ «ΕΚΚΛΗΣΙΑ ΠΟΛΩΝΙΑΣ,» *Ἐκκλησία* 6 (February 4, 1927), pp. 47–48.

⁴⁹ See: P. Tzoumerkas, «Ἡ Αὐτοκέφαλη Ἐκκλησία τῆς Πολωνίας κατὰ τὴν περίοδο τοῦ Β΄ Παγκοσμίου Πολέμου. Ἀνέκδοτο Ὑπόμνημα—Ἐκθεση τοῦ Ἀρχιεπισκόπου Γκρόδνο Σάββα (Sowietow) πρὸς τὸν Οἰκουμενικὸ Πατριάρχην Βενιαμίν (The Autocephalous Church of Poland during the Second World War. Unpublished Memorandum—Report by Archbishop Sawa of Grodno (Sowietow) to Ecumenical Patriarch Benjamin)», *Dialogue: Studies in Theology*, Hellenic Open University Press, Patras 2020, pp. 383–419.

⁵⁰ V. Feidas, *Ἐκκλησιαστικὴ Ἱστορία Γ΄—Ἀπὸ τὴν ἄλωση μέχρι σήμερον—1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III—From the Fall to*

During the tumultuous period following World War II, Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow (1871–1970) saw an opportunity to bring the Church of Poland under his jurisdiction. Consequently, he considered the autocephaly granted by the Ecumenical Patriarchate in 1924—recognized by all Orthodox Churches—as «non-existent.» This stance initiated the Russian Church’s plan to abolish the autocephaly of the Church of Poland. Russian hierarchs also engaged with some Orthodox Churches to clarify their intentions regarding the abolition of Polish autocephaly. A notable instance was the meeting between metropolitan Gregory of Leningrad (1870–1955) and archpriest Nikolai Koltsitski with Patriarch Christophoros II of Alexandria (1876–1967), which took place on December 2, 1946, at the headquarters of the Patriarchate of Alexandria. During this meeting, metropolitan Gregory questioned whether the Church of Poland should be autocephalous or autonomous and whether this issue should be discussed at a Pan-Orthodox meeting, which, as it later became apparent, the Church of Russia intended to hold in Moscow under the presidency of the Patriarch of Moscow.⁵¹ In the context of the meeting, metropolitan of Leningrad emphasized the urgent need for closer communication among the Orthodox Churches regarding such questions, while the Alexandrian primate, without specifically mentioning the Church of Poland, informed him that he was considering asking the Ecumenical Patriarch to convene a Council of Orthodox Churches «when things calm down.»⁵²

In June 1948, a Polish delegation led by bishop Timothy, with members including bishop George Korenistov (1900–1979), clerics Nikolai Linchevsky, Mikhail Kedrov, Eugene Naumov, and mr. Nikolai Semenovich Serebrennikov, was compelled to travel to Moscow.⁵³ On the

Today—1453–2014), op. cit., p. 621. А. Ведерников, «Внутреннее дело Польской Православной Церкви», in *Журнал Московской Патриархии* 8 (1950), pp. 47–48.

⁵¹ I. Ladas, (forthcoming), *The Efforts of the Church of Russia to gather the Orthodox Churches together in the Mid-20th Century (1945–1958)*.

⁵² Minutes recorded by Patriarch Christopher of Alexandria during his meeting with Metropolitan Gregory of Leningrad, Alexandria, December 2, 1946, in the *Reply of Patriarch Christopher of Alexandria to the Letter without Prot. No., dated August 5, 1947, from Patriarch Alexis of Moscow, Prot. No. 2312, dated October 9, 1947*: Archive of Archbishop Elpidophoros of America.

⁵³ At Moscow’s Vnukovo Airport, the delegation was met by Archbishop Vitaly of Dmitrov (1870–1950), Archpriest N. Koltsitski, Archimandrite Jeremiah, the Secretary of the Department of External Church Relations of the Patriarchate

first day, the Polish delegation met with metropolitan Nicholaos of Krutitsy and Kolomna (1891–1961) at the offices of the Moscow Patriarchate, and the following day they were received by Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow. During the meeting, the delegation declared that: 1. it recognizes the Tomos of Autocephaly of 1924 as uncanonical, 2. it requests from the «mother» Church of Russia its blessing for canonical autocephaly, 3. it ceases ecclesiastical communion with metropolitan Dionysius, due to his opposition to the «mother» Church of Russia and his repeated assertions in letters to the Patriarch of Moscow that the Church of Poland had received canonical autocephaly from the Ecumenical Patriarchate, 4. it breaks communion with all clergy and all people who share the aforementioned misconception of metropolitan Dionysius until they repent.⁵⁴

On June 22, 1948, Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow, in the presence of metropolitan Nicholaos of Krutitsy and Kolomna, archbishop Vitaly of Dmitrov, and bishop Nikon of Donetsk (1902–1956), presented to the Polish delegation an «Act» of the Church of Russia. According to this «Act», considering that the Church of Poland rejects the autocephaly of 1924, the Church of Russia: 1. restores ecclesiastical and liturgical communion with the Church of Poland, 2. grants it the right to organize as an autocephalous church, and 3. following the ratification by the Synod of Bishops of the Church of Russia of the autocephaly of the Church of Poland, the Church of Poland may elect its primate. Until that moment, the Church of Poland acquires the organization required by the canons for autocephaly. This «Act» thus constituted an assurance of granting autocephaly, as it would be effective after ratification by all the bishops of the Church of Russia. It eventually took full effect 7 months later, on November 22, 1948, when it received the signatures of all Russian bishops.⁵⁵

Additionally, Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow accepted a request from the Polish delegation to ordain archimandrite Mikhail Kedrov as bishop of Wroclaw, as there was agreement from the Polish authorities. Although

S.I. Filippov, the Vice Chairman of the Council for the Affairs of the Russian Orthodox Church S.K. Belyshev, and a representative of the Polish Embassy. As reported in the official journal of the Russian Church, the delegation was hosted at one of Moscow's finest hotels, the «National» Hotel.

⁵⁴ The Act of reunification of the Orthodox Church of Poland with the Orthodox Church of Russia and the granting of autocephaly, in A. Ведерников, «Внутреннее дело Польской Православной Церкви,» *op. cit.*, p. 43.

⁵⁵ «Польская Православная Церковь,» *Журнал Московской Патриархии* 3 (1949), p. 8.

there was no election of bishop Mikhail by the Church of Poland, his ordination took place on June 25 at the Patriarchal Cathedral in Moscow, conducted by Patriarch Alexis I. In his speech, the Patriarch highlighted that the restoration of ecclesiastical communion between the Church of Poland and the mother Church of Russia after a 25-year hiatus is a joyous event for both the Polish and Russian Churches. He added that the Polish Church, having now received the blessing of autocephaly from the Russian Church, must strive even harder to maintain the faith and traditions of the Orthodox Church.⁵⁶

On December 4, 1948, bishop Timothy expressed «deep gratitude» on behalf of the Church of Poland to Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow and noted «that the young autocephalous Orthodox Polish Church, being in close prayerful communion with the older sister Russian Church, will overcome all adversities and difficulties, will improve its internal life, and will contribute to the salvific work of establishing peace and justice on earth.»⁵⁷

Three years later, on April 19, 1951, the hierarchs of the Church of Poland gathered with the intent to elect a new primate. In this context, they deemed it prudent to request a hierarch from the Church of Russia, which appointed the former archbishop of Mukachevo and Uzhgorod, Makarios (1884–1961), as the primate of the Church of Poland. Formally, Makarios, who had joined the Church of Poland on May 15, 1951, was elected on July 7, 1951, and his enthronement as the primate of the Church of Poland took place the following day, Sunday, July 8, at the Cathedral of Warsaw,⁵⁸ in the presence of delegations from the Churches of Russia,⁵⁹ Romania,⁶⁰ and Bulgaria.⁶¹

⁵⁶ «Представители Польской Православной Церкви о своем посещении Москвы,» *Журнал Московской Патриархии* 7 (1948), p. 17.

⁵⁷ А. Ведерников, «Внутреннее дело Польской Православной Церкви,» *op. cit.*, p. 46.

⁵⁸ For detailed information on the enthronement of metropolitan Makarios, see: К. Ruzhitsky, «Церковное торжество в Варшаве,» *Журнал Московской Патриархии* 8 (1951), pp. 43–47.

⁵⁹ The Church of Russia was represented by Metropolitan John of Kiev (1877–1968) and the Archpriests К. Ruzhitsky and I. Malyushitsky.

⁶⁰ The Church of Romania was represented by Metropolitan Firmilian of Oltenia (1901–1972), Bishop Anthimos of Târgoviște (1908–1994), and Archpriest I. Batznoi.

⁶¹ The Church of Bulgaria was represented by Metropolitan Nikodimos of Silistra

Two days after his enthronement, metropolitan Makarios officially announced his election to the primates of the Orthodox Churches. In these letters, he noted, among other things, that «recently the Church of Poland restored communion with its mother Church of Russia, which, showing deep understanding of the new circumstances through an Act on June 22, 1948, blessed its young daughter for autocephalous organization and the election of a primate.»⁶² On August 4, 1951, the Patriarch of Moscow expressed his satisfaction and emphasized the fact that the Church of Russia, attentive to the needs of the Church of Poland, granted permission for metropolitan Makarios to serve this Church.⁶³

Following the irregularities that had occurred, the relations between the Church of Poland and the Ecumenical Patriarchate had almost ceased, and the Mother Church of Constantinople was «unaware» of the situation there. The Ecumenical Patriarchate did not commemorate in the Diptychs the name of the purported primate, Makarios, but continued to commemorate the name of Metropolitan Dionysius, who was under restriction.

The Ecumenical Patriarchate did not respond to the letter from Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow dated July 10, 1948, in which he announced the granting of autocephaly to the Church of Poland.⁶⁴ All related correspondence was referred to the Canonical Committee,⁶⁵ which opined that the ongoing

(1895–1980) and the Archpriests F. Kocel and A. Andreev.

⁶² «Известительная Грамота Митрополита Варшавского и всея Польши Макария,» *Журнал Московской Патриархии* 9 (1951), pp. 7–8.

⁶³ «Послание Патриарха Алексия Митрополиту Варшавскому и всея Польши Макарию,» *Журнал Московской Патриархии* 9 (1951), p. 9.

⁶⁴ Letter from Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow, without Prot. No., dated July 10, 1948: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod.

⁶⁵ Letter from Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow to Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras, Prot.No., dated July 11, 1949: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod. Letter from Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras to Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow, without Prot. No., dated February 23, 1950: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod. Response from Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow to the letters without Prot. No., dated February 23, 1950, from Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras, Prot. No. [blank], dated July 3, 1950: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod. Letter from Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow to the Ecumenical Patriarchate, Prot. No. 156, dated January 25, 1952: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod.

silence of the Ecumenical Patriarchate could be construed as consent.⁶⁶ The Committee reviewed 1. the letters from Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow and 2. the letter from the purported metropolitan Makarios announcing both his election as primate of the Church of Poland and the blessing of Patriarch Alexis I. The Committee decided that both letters should be responded to, based on canonical arguments, but any direct response to the purported Metropolitan Makarios should be avoided, as the Ecumenical Patriarchate only recognized metropolitan Dionysius.

In this spirit, Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras thanked Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow for his interest in informing the Ecumenical Patriarchate about the developments, while also emphasizing that the Ecumenical Patriarchate, due to historical ties to the ecclesiastical region of Poland and the responsibilities and special position arising from the sacred canons and the longstanding practices of the Church, could not ignore or be indifferent to the Orthodox Church of Poland. He reminded that the Ecumenical Patriarchate had issued a Synodal and Patriarchal Tomos elevating the Church of Poland to autocephalous status in 1924. He also expressed hope that the Patriarchate of Moscow would respect the acts recognized by all Churches for the past twenty-five years, for the sake of Orthodox unity.

On the other hand, the chief secretariat of the Ecumenical Patriarchate assured the secretariat of the Church of Poland of the receipt of the letter signed by «Metropolitan of Warsaw and All Poland Makarios» and reiterated the special affection and deep practical interest it held for the Christ-like progress of the Church of Poland. Additionally, it clarified that the Patriarchate of Constantinople recognizes His Beatitude Dionysius as the metropolitan of Warsaw and All Poland, who has shepherded the Church of Poland since 1924. For this reason, it requested the chief secretary of the Holy Synod of the Church of Poland to provide relevant information to the Church of Constantinople.⁶⁷

It should be noted that in the Church of Poland, only about 100 sacred

⁶⁶ Report of the Canonical Committee, Prot. No. 542, dated September 17, 1951: Archive B' 86, pp. 486–88.

⁶⁷ Letter from Metropolitan Makarios to Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras, Prot. No. 7, dated July 10, 1951: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod. Response from the Secretariat of the Ecumenical Patriarchate to the Secretariat of the Church of Poland: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod. Session of the Holy and Sacred Synod dated September 18, 1951: Archive B' 86, pp. 486–88.

temples and a single monastery remained, while the confiscation of what little ecclesiastical property was left necessitated financial support from the people.⁶⁸ Furthermore, the Church of Poland had lost the vast majority of its clergy, theologians, and flock, which had decreased from approximately five million to just four hundred fifty thousand.⁶⁹

The resolution of the Polish issue

The preparation for the Holy and Great Council of the Orthodox Church, convened by Ecumenical Patriarch Bartholomew I on the island of Crete in 2016, officially began on July 9, 1923. On this date, the Holy and Sacred Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate unanimously decided to accept the resolution of the Pan-Orthodox Congress (1923) and to convene a Council of the Orthodox Churches in 1925 on the occasion of the 1600th anniversary of the First Ecumenical Council held in Nicaea.⁷⁰

However, the preparation for the Council languished from 1930 onwards due to the outbreak of World War II. In 1951, Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras I vigorously restarted the preparations for the convocation of a Council of the Orthodox Churches and placed the issue under the scrutiny of the individual Orthodox Churches.⁷¹ Despite the urgent need for an assembly of the Orthodox Churches, there were several difficulties that needed to be neutralized before its convocation. There were many pending issues, with the most significant being the smoothing of inter-Orthodox relations to achieve the desired unity and the presence of all the individual Autocephalous Churches in a gathering that would have a Pan-Orthodox character.

Given the Church of Poland's canonically ambiguous status, the Church of Russia: a) did not recognize the autocephaly of the Church of Poland,

⁶⁸ V. Feidas, *Ἐκκλησιαστική Ἱστορία Γ'—Ἀπὸ τὴν ἄλωση μέχρι σήμερον—1453–2014 (Ecclesiastical History Volume III—From the Fall to Today—1453–2014)*, op. cit., p. 622–3.

⁶⁹ P. Tzoumerkas, «Ἡ αυτοκέφαλη ορθόδοξη Ἐκκλησία τῆς Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland),» op. cit., p. 325.

⁷⁰ See in detail: I. Ladas, *Holy and Great Council of the Orthodox Church 2016. Preparation - Procedures*, Doctoral Dissertation: Thessaloniki 2023.

⁷¹ Patriarchal Encyclical Letters to the Primates of the local Orthodox Churches, Prot. No. 108, dated February 12, 1951: Archive of Archbishop Elpidophoros of America.

granted in 1924, b) proceeded to «grant» a «new autocephaly» to this Church in 1948, and c) «proclaimed as autocephalous» the autonomous Church of Czechoslovakia. Thus, the question arose: what would be the stance of the Church of Russia in the case that, as would be proper, the archbishop of Warsaw, Dionysius, was invited, and on the other hand, as could not be done, the primate of the Church considered as autocephalous by the Church of Russia, the Church of Czechoslovakia, was not invited? The main issue was how the scenario where the Church of Russia would refuse to participate in the Pre-Council, provided that the two uncanonical acts were not recognized beforehand, would be handled. And if this occurred, would it also draw other Churches? Generally, would convening a Pre-Council, not involving all Orthodox Churches, be beneficial? Wouldn't this approach split the unity of the Orthodox Church into two factions with a pronounced ethnic character?⁷²

The Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras I, considering on one hand the need for a gathering of the Orthodox Churches, and on the other hand the fact that the difficulties existing for the convening of the Pre-Council required significant time to be resolved, conceived the idea of convening a preparatory body for the upcoming Pre-Council, similar to the Preliminary Committee of the Orthodox Churches convened in 1930. The convocation of this body appeared as an ideal solution to overcome the deadlock. Consequently, addressing the Polish issue was urgent, as the Church of Poland needed to participate in the body to be convened, given that the planned Pan-Orthodox Conference needed to find the Orthodox Church united, not fragmented into factions and alignments. Meanwhile, there was a recession in the relations between the Ecumenical Patriarchate and the Church of Russia, indicated by a letter sent by the latter to Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras I in the early 1960s, which listed the differences between the two Churches but did not include the Polish issue among them.⁷³

On May 24, 1960, the Committee on Pan-Orthodox Issues convened and thoroughly examined the Polish issue. Considering the situation and aligning with the demands of the times and the well-understood interests of the Orthodox Church, the Committee engaged in a detailed study to

⁷² Idem, p. 4.

⁷³ Letter from Patriarch Alexis I of Moscow to Ecumenical Patriarch Athenagoras, Prot. No. 189, dated February 25, 1960: Archive of the Secretariat of the Holy and Sacred Synod.

ultimately enable the invitation and representation of the Church of Poland at the First Pan-Orthodox Conference. After a thorough examination of the Polish issue, the Committee judged that the issue still persisted as a canonical consequence for the Ecumenical Patriarchate. However, the favorable conditions that had developed in the relationships of the Ecumenical Patriarchate with the other Churches, as well as the expressed wish and desire to resolve any misunderstandings, should lead the Ecumenical Patriarchate to reposition the Polish issue in a more favorable direction towards the involved Churches, without affecting the interests of the Church. Moreover, with the death of metropolitan Dionysius and formally, the existing difficulties were resolved because the Ecumenical Patriarchate was released from the moral and canonical obligations to the person of the recognized metropolitan Dionysius. Thus, the Committee judged that the presence of then «metropolitan» Makarios, or even his departing, was not a concern of the mother Church but was a matter of internal jurisdiction of the Church of Poland.⁷⁴

Based on the above, the Committee on Pan-Orthodox Issues, in view of the forthcoming Pan-Orthodox Conference in Rhodes and the need to invite the Church of Poland, recommended that invitation letters be sent, addressed to «His Beatitude the archbishop of Warsaw and all Poland, Makarios,» or his successor (especially since he never ceased communication with the Ecumenical Patriarchate and on every festive or other occasion sent letters). The sending of these invitation letters would also be considered as a restoration of the canonical relations between the two Churches on its own.⁷⁵

Metropolitan Makarios passed away on March 2, 1961,⁷⁶ and archbishop

⁷⁴ Report of the Committee on Pan-Orthodox Issues, Prot. No. 295, dated May 24, 1960: Archive of Archbishop Elpidophoros of America.

⁷⁵ *Idem.*

⁷⁶ The canonical Primate of the Church of Poland, Metropolitan Dionysius, passed away on March 15, 1960, while Metropolitan Macarius passed away on March 2, 1961. On May 5, 1961, Archbishop Timothy of Białystok and Gdańsk was elected as Metropolitan of Warsaw, but he passed away on May 20, 1962. From 1962 to 1965, Archbishop George of Łódź and Poznań (1900–1979) served as locum tenens of the metropolitan throne, and on May 26, 1965, Archbishop Stephen of Białystok and Gdańsk was elected as Metropolitan of Warsaw, who passed away on March 26, 1969. On January 24, 1970, Bishop Basil of Wrocław and Szczecin was elected Metropolitan of Warsaw, serving until his passing on

of Bialystok and Gdansk Timothy was elected as the Primate of the Church of Poland. He immediately announced his election through a letter to the Ecumenical Patriarchate. Consequently, with the death of the metropolitan of Warsaw Dionysius, and the death/replacement of the individuals who had been directly involved in the uncanonical actions, the existing difficulties were formally resolved because the Ecumenical Patriarchate was released from its moral and canonical obligations towards the individuals it recognized as canonical primates. In this context, the Holy and Sacred Synod of the Ecumenical Patriarchate, with affectionate regard, provided its blessing for the restoration of the canonical status of the Church of Poland and decided to invite metropolitan Timothy to the First Pan-Orthodox Conference.⁷⁷

The Orthodox Churches in canonical communion with the Ecumenical Patriarchate were comprehensively informed about the preparation of the First Pan-Orthodox Conference on May 4, 1961, when it was confirmed that the assembly could be convened within the same year.⁷⁸ In contrast, the Church of Poland received the Patriarchal invitation letters once the canonical issues preventing its participation were resolved. Consequently, the Church of Poland was invited on June 9, 1961.⁷⁹ The dispatch of these invitation letters was considered a de facto restoration of canonical relations between the two Churches. With the sending of the invitation letters, Timothy of Warsaw was recognized de facto as the successor to Dionysius of Warsaw. This recognition was not in strict accordance with the sacred canons but was done out of pastoral care and with the sole aim of benefiting the Church.

Conclusions

After the end of World War I and the establishment of an independent

February 11, 1998. He was succeeded by the current Primate of the Church of Poland, Metropolitan Sava.

⁷⁷ Session dated August 24, 1961: AHSS: File No. 124 «First Pan-Orthodox Conference II».

⁷⁸ Patriarchal Letters to the Primates of the local Orthodox Churches regarding the convening of the Pan-Orthodox Conference, Prot. No. 310, dated May 4, 1961: AHSS: File No. 217 «First Pan-Orthodox Conference I».

⁷⁹ Patriarchal Letters to Metropolitan Timothy of Warsaw regarding the convening of the Pan-Orthodox Conference, Prot. No. 310, dated June 9, 1961: AHSS: File No. 217 «First Pan-Orthodox Conference I».

Polish state, clergy and orthodox believers, supported by state authorities, appealed to the Ecumenical Patriarchate, requesting that the Church of Poland be elevated to autocephalous status. The Ecumenical Patriarchate reviewed the request and, for both canonical and historical reasons, issued a Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos granting full ecclesiastical independence to the Church of Poland on November 13, 1924, during the patriarchate of Gregory VII.

The establishment of the autocephaly of the Church of Poland differs significantly from the way other Slavic churches have gained ecclesiastical independence, as it did not involve a unilateral declaration of autocephaly by the church itself. In this case, the desire to create an independent Orthodox church belonged to the Christian community and the state authorities. The Orthodox Christians living in the newly established state of Poland did not proclaim their ecclesiastical independence themselves; instead, recognizing the ancient ties that existed with the Ecumenical Patriarchate, they approached it and submitted a request for guidance in their spiritual life. The mother church responded affectionately to this request and elevated the Church of Poland to the status of an autocephalous local church.

During World War II (1939–1945), Nazi Germany invaded Poland, and the Soviet Union annexed its eastern territories, resulting in a communist regime. Most of the Orthodox population fell under the ecclesiastical jurisdiction of the Russian Church, which attempted to subjugate the autocephalous Church of Poland. Initially, the Russian Church made contact to abolish the existing autocephaly, later declaring it illegal and non-existent, and organized a new one, condemning all clerics involved in the legitimate autocephaly as guilty. Simultaneously, it forced the metropolitan of Warsaw, Dionysius, to resign and seek forgiveness from the Church of Russia for the «sin» he committed when he appealed to the jurisdiction of the Ecumenical Patriarchate to receive autocephaly. In this context, it placed the former Mukachevo and Uzhgorod Makarios as the head of this Church in replacement of the removed metropolitan Dionysius. This way, the Polish issue arose, broadly involving all Orthodox Churches, both from the North and the South, but primarily concerning the Ecumenical Patriarchate and the Church of Poland on one hand, and the Russian Church, positioned as the «mother church», on the other.

The Church of Constantinople did not accept the uncanonical and

irregular actions carried out in the Church of Poland. Particularly, after the repose of metropolitan Dionysius on March 15, 1960, there ensued a complete cessation of canonical relations between the Ecumenical Throne and the Church of Poland for about a year. Metropolitan Makarios, despite his efforts, until his own repose on March 2, 1961, failed to establish canonical relations either with the Ecumenical Patriarchate or with the rest of the Orthodox world, as for the majority of his tenure, metropolitan Dionysius was still alive and recognized as the primate. Throughout this period, the exchanged letters on both sides aimed at securing the tense situation and were addressed either to metropolitan Dionysius or to the secretariat of the Church of Poland.

The Ecumenical Patriarchate, upon restarting the preparations for convening the Holy and Great Council of the Orthodox Church, was deeply aware that the Polish issue, if continued, would disrupt the unity of the Church. Consequently, the mother Church did not wish for this matter to be placed on an erroneous basis and presented as the cause of the division of ecclesiastical unity and an obstacle to the convening of the First Pan-Orthodox Conference. Therefore, characterized by a broadminded approach, it seemed prepared to find a *modus vivendi* and to invite the Church of Poland, under its then-current form, to the First Pan-Orthodox Conference.

The action of the Ecumenical Patriarchate was not an expansion of its jurisdiction, as unfortunately stated by the Church of Russia, but rather a lofty obligation of ecclesiastical providence and insight towards a troubled Orthodox Church. Had it remained indifferent, it would have fallen short of its historical and canonical responsibilities. It is well-documented historically that the Ecumenical Patriarchate has offered fraternal support to several Orthodox Churches during their trials, without ever seeking to dominate or influence their internal organization and life, simply fulfilling its mandated duty. In contrast, the Church of Russia sought to use the Church of Poland as a tool for political expedience or as an ecclesiastical instrument to echo its views within the framework of inter-Orthodox relations.⁸⁰

In conclusion, it must be emphasized that the decision of the Ecumenical Patriarchate to invite the Church of Poland to the First Pan-Orthodox

⁸⁰ P. Tzoumerkas, «Η αυτοκέφαλη ορθόδοξη Εκκλησία της Πολωνίας (The Autocephalous Orthodox Church of Poland),» *op. cit.*, p. 281.

Conference, thereby restoring canonical order, was perceived by some as an act of recognizing the preceding events—an entirely mistaken interpretation. There was never any recognition of the self-willed, arbitrarily, and uncanonically granted autocephaly by the Church of Russia. On the contrary, what transpired was considered from the start as invalid and without effect, and the invitation served to restore the autocephaly granted in 1924. References and statements regarding the so-called autocephaly of 1948 express contempt for ecclesiastical and canonical order, and a denial in form and substance of the canonical autocephaly granted to the Church of Poland.

This year marks the centennial anniversary of the granting of full ecclesiastical independence to the Church of Poland. In this context, the Holy Synod in Poland has decided to organize various celebratory events,⁸¹ giving the celebrations a religious, liturgical, and pastoral dimension.⁸² The climax of these festivities is on November 13, 2024, the 100th anniversary of the signing of the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos of autocephaly by Ecumenical Patriarch Gregory VII.⁸³ On this day, the primate of the Church, metropolitan Sava,⁸⁴ will officiate at the Cathedral of Saint Mary

⁸¹ See for example: «Symposium naukowe w Zamościu,» available at <https://www.orthodox.pl/symposium-naukowe-w-zamosciu/>, last accessed October 20, 2024. «Symposium naukowe w Białej Podlaskiej,» available at <https://www.orthodox.pl/symposium-naukowe-w-bialej-podlaskiej/>, last accessed October 20, 2024. «Konferencja o kobiecie w historii 100-lecia autokefalii,» available at <https://www.orthodox.pl/konferencja-o-kobiecie-w-historii-100-lecia-autokefalii/>, last accessed October 20, 2024. «Konferencja naukowa w Lublinie,» available at <https://www.orthodox.pl/konferencja-naukowa-w-lublinie/>, last accessed October 20, 2024. «Prezentacja projektu: '100 lat autokefalii. 1000 lat historii',» available at <https://www.orthodox.pl/prezentacja-projektu-100-lat-autokefalii-1000-lat-historii/>, last accessed October 20, 2024. «Wyniki konkursu plastycznego dot. 100-lecia autokefalii,» available at <https://www.orthodox.pl/wyniki-konkursu-plastycznego-dot-100-lecie-autokefalii/>, last accessed October 20, 2024.

⁸² Session of the Holy Synod of the Church of Poland dated October 24, 2023.

⁸³ Encyclical of the Holy Synod of the Church of Poland on the occasion of the 100th anniversary of its elevation to autocephalous status. «Przesłanie Św. Soboru Biskupów Polskiego Autokefalicznego Kościoła Prawosławnego z okazji 100-lecia Jego autokefalii,» available at <https://www.orthodox.pl/67527-2/>, last accessed October 20, 2024.

⁸⁴ The Primate of the Church of Poland, Metropolitan Sava, in the preface of

Magdalene in Warsaw, attended by the President of the Republic of Poland, Andrzej Duda, under whose patronage the celebratory events are held.⁸⁵ This clearly demonstrates that the Church of Poland itself recognizes and honors the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos of 1924, through which it received full ecclesiastical independence and was incorporated into the family of Orthodox Autocephalous Churches.

the book *Cerkiew prawosławna w Polsce i jej droga do autokefalii*, which is dedicated to the jubilee anniversary of the Church of Poland, aptly notes that the Patriarchal and Synodal Tomos of 1924 was recognized by all local Churches, while the Church of Russia, which was subjugated by the communists, only recognized it in 1948. A. Mironowicz, *Cerkiew prawosławna w Polsce i jej droga do autokefalii*, Warszawska Metropolia Prawosławna, Warsaw 2023.

⁸⁵ «Patronat Honorowy Prezydenta RP,» available at <https://www.orthodox.pl/patronat-honorowy-prezydenta-rp/>, last accessed October 20, 2024